
Ichthyop Python package (1.1.0)

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GETTING STARTED

1.1 Requirements

To use the Ichthyop Python package, the following libraries are required:

- `netCDF4` and `xarray` for the manipulation of NetCDF files.
- `matplotlib` and `cartopy` for the spatial representation of Ichthyop outputs.
- `pysnp` for the manipulation of shapefiles.

1.2 Installing the package

1.2.1 PIP install

The code can be installed using Python Package Index (PIP) as follows:

```
` pip install ichthyop `
```

1.2.2 From source

The code can also be installed from source files. First, download the code from the Git repository:

```
` git clone https://github.com/ichthyop/ichthyop-python `
```

Then, type:

```
` python setup.py install `
```


READING OUTPUTS

2.1 Reading and selecting data

The reading of Ichthyop datasets is performed by using the `read.extract_dataset()` function. In addition to the path of NetCDF output file, the function can take optional arguments allowing to extract a subperiod or a limited number of drifters:

- drifters are selected through the `dmin`, `dmax` and `dstride` arguments: `slice(dmin, dmax+1, dstride)`
- the time-period is selected through the `tmin`, `tmax` and `tstride` arguments: `slice(tmin, tmax+1, tstride)`

If all these arguments are set to `None`, the entire dataset is read.

```
import ichthyop.read as ichread

filename = '_static/ichthyop-example.nc'

# read the entire dataset
data_all = ichread.extract_dataset(filename)

# reading the 11 first time indexes
data_first_time = ichread.extract_dataset(filename, tmax=10)

# reading the 10 last time indexes
data_last_time = ichread.extract_dataset(filename, tmin=-10)

# reading one time step out of 2
data_tstride = ichread.extract_dataset(filename, tstride=2)

# extracts the trajectories of drifters number 50 to 61
data_subdrift = ichread.extract_dataset(filename, dmin=50, dmax=61)

# extracts the trajectories of drifters number 50
data_subdrift = ichread.extract_dataset(filename, dmin=50, dmax=50)
```

```
In [1]: data_all
```

```
Out[1]:
```

```
<xarray.Dataset>
```

```
Dimensions:      (time: 367, drifter: 2000, edge: 3360, latlon: 2)
```

```
Coordinates:
```

```
* time          (time) float64 7.964e+08 7.965e+08 ... 8.279e+08 8.279e+08
```

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```

* drifter      (drifter) int64 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 ... 1994 1995 1996 1997 1998 1999
Dimensions without coordinates: edge, latlon
Data variables:
  lat          (time, drifter) float32 ...
  lon          (time, drifter) float32 ...
  mortality    (time, drifter) int32 ...
  region_edge  (edge, latlon) float32 ...
Attributes: (12/49)
  transport_dimension:      2d
  release.schedule.is_enabled: false
  release.schedule.events:  "year 2017 month 05 day 13 at 1...
  app.time.initial_time:    year 2017 month 12 day 30 at 12:00
  app.time.transport_duration: 365 day(s) 01 hour(s) 00 minute(s)
  app.time.time_step:       7200
  ...                       ...
  dataset.oscar.mask_var:   mask
  dataset.oscar.mask_file:  mask_2010_2017.nc
  xml_file:                 /home1/datawork/nbarrier/ichthy...
  nb_zones:                 0
  history:                  Fri Mar 27 18:39:20 2020: ncks ...
  NCO:                      netCDF Operators version 4.8.0 ...

```

In [2]: data_first_time**Out[2]:**

```

<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:      (time: 11, drifter: 2000, edge: 3360, latlon: 2)
Coordinates:
  * time          (time) float64 7.964e+08 7.965e+08 ... 7.972e+08 7.973e+08
  * drifter      (drifter) int64 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 ... 1994 1995 1996 1997 1998 1999
Dimensions without coordinates: edge, latlon
Data variables:
  lat          (time, drifter) float32 ...
  lon          (time, drifter) float32 ...
  mortality    (time, drifter) int32 ...
  region_edge  (edge, latlon) float32 ...
Attributes: (12/49)
  transport_dimension:      2d
  release.schedule.is_enabled: false
  release.schedule.events:  "year 2017 month 05 day 13 at 1...
  app.time.initial_time:    year 2017 month 12 day 30 at 12:00
  app.time.transport_duration: 365 day(s) 01 hour(s) 00 minute(s)
  app.time.time_step:       7200
  ...                       ...
  dataset.oscar.mask_var:   mask
  dataset.oscar.mask_file:  mask_2010_2017.nc
  xml_file:                 /home1/datawork/nbarrier/ichthy...
  nb_zones:                 0
  history:                  Fri Mar 27 18:39:20 2020: ncks ...
  NCO:                      netCDF Operators version 4.8.0 ...

```

In [3]: data_last_time**Out[3]:**

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```

<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:      (time: 10, drifter: 2000, edge: 3360, latlon: 2)
Coordinates:
  * time         (time) float64 8.272e+08 8.273e+08 ... 8.279e+08 8.279e+08
  * drifter      (drifter) int64 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 ... 1994 1995 1996 1997 1998 1999
Dimensions without coordinates: edge, latlon
Data variables:
  lat           (time, drifter) float32 ...
  lon           (time, drifter) float32 ...
  mortality     (time, drifter) int32 ...
  region_edge   (edge, latlon) float32 ...
Attributes: (12/49)
  transport_dimension:      2d
  release.schedule.is_enabled: false
  release.schedule.events:  "year 2017 month 05 day 13 at 1...
  app.time.initial_time:    year 2017 month 12 day 30 at 12:00
  app.time.transport_duration: 365 day(s) 01 hour(s) 00 minute(s)
  app.time.time_step:       7200
  ...                       ...
  dataset.oscar.mask_var:   mask
  dataset.oscar.mask_file:  mask_2010_2017.nc
  xml_file:                 /home1/datawork/nbarrier/ichthy...
  nb_zones:                 0
  history:                  Fri Mar 27 18:39:20 2020: ncks ...
  NCO:                      netCDF Operators version 4.8.0 ...

```

In [4]: data_tstride**Out[4]:**

```

<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:      (time: 184, drifter: 2000, edge: 3360, latlon: 2)
Coordinates:
  * time         (time) float64 7.964e+08 7.966e+08 ... 8.278e+08 8.279e+08
  * drifter      (drifter) int64 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 ... 1994 1995 1996 1997 1998 1999
Dimensions without coordinates: edge, latlon
Data variables:
  lat           (time, drifter) float32 ...
  lon           (time, drifter) float32 ...
  mortality     (time, drifter) int32 ...
  region_edge   (edge, latlon) float32 ...
Attributes: (12/49)
  transport_dimension:      2d
  release.schedule.is_enabled: false
  release.schedule.events:  "year 2017 month 05 day 13 at 1...
  app.time.initial_time:    year 2017 month 12 day 30 at 12:00
  app.time.transport_duration: 365 day(s) 01 hour(s) 00 minute(s)
  app.time.time_step:       7200
  ...                       ...
  dataset.oscar.mask_var:   mask
  dataset.oscar.mask_file:  mask_2010_2017.nc
  xml_file:                 /home1/datawork/nbarrier/ichthy...
  nb_zones:                 0
  history:                  Fri Mar 27 18:39:20 2020: ncks ...

```

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```

NCO: netCDF Operators version 4.8.0 ...

In [5]: data_subdrift
Out[5]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:      (time: 367, drifter: 1, edge: 3360, latlon: 2)
Coordinates:
  * time          (time) float64 7.964e+08 7.965e+08 ... 8.279e+08 8.279e+08
  * drifter       (drifter) int64 50
Dimensions without coordinates: edge, latlon
Data variables:
  lat             (time, drifter) float32 ...
  lon             (time, drifter) float32 ...
  mortality       (time, drifter) int32 ...
  region_edge     (edge, latlon) float32 ...
Attributes: (12/49)
  transport_dimension: 2d
  release.schedule.is_enabled: false
  release.schedule.events: "year 2017 month 05 day 13 at 1...
  app.time.initial_time: year 2017 month 12 day 30 at 12:00
  app.time.transport_duration: 365 day(s) 01 hour(s) 00 minute(s)
  app.time.time_step: 7200
  ...
  dataset.oscar.mask_var: mask
  dataset.oscar.mask_file: mask_2010_2017.nc
  xml_file: /home1/datawork/nbarrier/ichthy...
  nb_zones: 0
  history: Fri Mar 27 18:39:20 2020: ncks ...
NCO: netCDF Operators version 4.8.0 ...

```

2.2 Extracting date

Instead of using numerical time, it may be useful to use a more readable date. This may be achieved by using the `read.extract_date()` function, which allows to convert numerical time into `datetime.datetime` objects. If no arguments is provided by the function, it is assumed that the units are in second since the time origin, which is provided in the input file as the origin attribute of the time variable.

Note that this function overwrites the original `time` coordinates in numerical time.

```

import ichthyop.read as ichread
import ichthyop.plot as ichplot
import pylab as plt

filename = '_static/ichthyop-example.nc'
#filename = '../_static/ichthyop-example.nc'

# extracts the trajectories of drifters numbers with a step of 1000
data = ichread.extract_dataset(filename, dstride=1000)

# creation of the date attribute
ichread.extract_date(data)

```

```
In [6]: data['time']
```

```
Out[6]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray 'time' (time: 367)>
array([cftime.DatetimeGregorian(2017, 12, 30, 12, 0, 0, 0, has_year_zero=False),
       cftime.DatetimeGregorian(2017, 12, 31, 12, 0, 0, 0, has_year_zero=False),
       cftime.DatetimeGregorian(2018, 1, 1, 12, 0, 0, 0, has_year_zero=False),
       ...,
       cftime.DatetimeGregorian(2018, 12, 29, 12, 0, 0, 0, has_year_zero=False),
       cftime.DatetimeGregorian(2018, 12, 30, 12, 0, 0, 0, has_year_zero=False),
       cftime.DatetimeGregorian(2018, 12, 30, 14, 0, 0, 0, has_year_zero=False)],
      dtype=object)
```

```
Coordinates:
```

```
* time      (time) object 2017-12-30 12:00:00 ... 2018-12-30 14:00:00
```


3.1 Drawing trajectories

The reading of Ichthyop datasets is performed by using the `plot.map_traj()` function.

```
import ichthyop.read as ichread
import ichthyop.plot as ichplot
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import cartopy.crs as ccrs
import cartopy.feature as cfeature

filename = '_static/ichthyop-example.nc'

# extracts the trajectories of drifters numbers with a step of 1000
data = ichread.extract_dataset(filename, dstride=1000)

# size of the points
pointsize = 20

# plot trajectories without colors
fig = plt.figure()
ax = plt.axes(projection=ccrs.PlateCarree())
ichplot.map_traj(data, layout='filled', size=pointsize)
plt.title('No col.')
plt.savefig('_static/map1.png', bbox_inches='tight')
plt.close(fig)

# plot trajectories with colors associated with drifter
fig = plt.figure()
ax = plt.axes(projection=ccrs.PlateCarree())
ichplot.map_traj(data, layout='filled', color='drifter', size=pointsize)
plt.title('Drifter')
plt.savefig('_static/map2.png', bbox_inches='tight')
extent = ax.get_extent()

plt.close(fig)

# plot trajectories with colors associated with time
fig = plt.figure()
ax = plt.axes(projection=ccrs.PlateCarree())
ichplot.map_traj(data, layout='etopo', color='time', size=pointsize)
```

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```
plt.title('Time')
ax.set_extent(extent)
ax.add_feature(cfeature.COASTLINE)
plt.savefig('_static/map3.png', bbox_inches='tight')
plt.close(fig)
```

No col.

Drifter

3.2 Movies

The `plot.make_movie()` allows to make movies of the drifter trajectories.

This function makes a series of `.png` files: `'temp_00000.png'`, `'temp_00001.png'`, etc. These files can be converted into a movie by using either `_mencoder` or `_ffmpeg`. This can be done from the terminal:

```
ffmpeg -y -framerate 24 -pattern_type glob -i 'temp*.png' -qscale:v 1 movie.avi
```

or directly from python

```
import os
os.system("ffmpeg -y -framerate 24 -pattern_type glob -i 'temp*.png' -qscale:v 1 movie.
↪avi")
```

The `-y` option allows overwriting without asking, the `-framerate` option defines the number of frames per second, the `-pattern_type glob -i 'temp*.png'` option defines the names of the `.png` files that will be used, and the `-qscale:v 1` is the quality factor.

```
import ichthyop.read as ichread
import ichthyop.plot as ichplot
import pylab as plt
import os

filename = '_static/ichthyop-example.nc'
```

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```
# extracts the trajectories of drifters numbers with a step of 1000
data = ichread.extract_dataset(filename, dstride=100, tmin=0, tmax=150)

# transforms the time coordinates into dates
ichread.extract_date(data)

# size of the points
pointsize = 15

# draws the figures that will be used to make the movie
# priov
extent = [27.007700909458563, 84.9354467498432, -39.823827920685424, -12.99684411453186]
dirout = '_static'
ichplot.make_movie(data, extent=extent, dirout=dirout, layout='etopo', size=pointsize)

os.system("ffmpeg -y -framerate 24 -pattern_type glob -i '%s/temp*.png' -codec:v,
↪ libtheora -qscale:v 1 %s/movie.ogg" %(dirout, dirout))
```

4.1 Reading outputs

<code>read.extract_dataset(filename[, dmin, dmax, ...])</code>	Reads an Ichthyop output file.
<code>read.extract_date(data[, units, calendar])</code>	Transformation of the time attribute from numerical time into <code>datetime.datetime</code> objects.

4.1.1 `ichthyop.read.extract_dataset`

`ichthyop.read.extract_dataset(filename, dmin=None, dmax=None, dstride=None, tmin=None, tmax=None, tstride=None)`

Reads an Ichthyop output file. Possibility to extract only a subspan of drifters or time.

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – Input file
- **dmin** (*int*) – First drifter index to read. Default is 0.
- **dmax** (*int*) – Last drifter index to read. Default is ND-1.
- **dstride** (*int*) – Drifter stride (default is 1).
- **tmin** (*int*) – First time index to read. Default is 0.
- **tmax** (*int*) – Last time index to read. Default is NT-1.
- **tstride** (*int*) – Time stride (default is 1).

Returns

A xarray dataset containing the file variables.

Return type

`xarray.Dataset`

4.1.2 `ichthyop.read.extract_date`

`ichthyop.read.extract_date(data, units=None, calendar=None)`

Transformation of the time attribute from numerical time into `datetime.datetime` objects.

If no time units is provided, it is assumed that the units are in seconds since the time origin, which is provided in the file as the origin attribute of the time variable in the format `year 2013 month 01 day 01 at 00:00`.

If no calendar is provided, the calendar attribute of the time variable is used.

Parameters

- **data** (*xarray.Dataset*) – Input dataset
- **units** (*str*) – Time units.
- **calendar** (*str*) – Time calendar

4.2 Plotting outputs

<code>plot.plot_traj(data[, color, size, alpha])</code>	Plots the trajectories given a certain basemap.
<code>plot.make_movie(data, extent[, dirout, ...])</code>	Draws a series of <code>.png</code> files, containing the position of each drifter at a given time-step.

4.2.1 `ichthyop.plot.plot_traj`

`ichthyop.plot.plot_traj(data, color='black', size=5, alpha=1)`

Plots the trajectories given a certain basemap. Used to avoid redefining the basemap in the drawing of movies.

Parameters

- **data** (*xarray*) – Input dataset
- **color** (*str*) – Color used in the scatter plot
- **size** (*int*) – Size points
- **alpha** (*float*) – Transparency (1=full, 0=transparent)

4.2.2 `ichthyop.plot.make_movie`

`ichthyop.plot.make_movie(data, extent, dirout='./, layout='lines', size=5)`

Draws a series of `.png` files, containing the position of each drifter at a given time-step.

Dots are coloured as a function of the drifter index. These files can then be merged into a movie using for instance `ffmpeg` or `mencoder`.

Parameters

- **data** (*xarray.Dataset*) – The input dataset
- **extent** (*list*) – Geographical extent [`lonmin`, `lonmax`, `latmin`, `latmax`]
- **layout** (*str*) – The map background ('lines', 'fill' or 'etopo')
- **size** (*int*) – The dot size

4.3 Manipulating shapes

<code>shape.Shape(longitude, latitude, name, typename)</code>	Shape object
---	--------------

4.3.1 `ichthyop.shape.Shape`

class `ichthyop.shape.Shape(longitude, latitude, name, typename)`

Shape object

`__init__(longitude, latitude, name, typename)`

Initialisation of the class.

Parameters

- **longitude** (*numpy.array*) – Longitude of the shape polygon
- **latitude** (*numpy.array*) – Latitude of the shape polygon
- **name** (*numpy.array*) – Name of the shape polygon
- **typename** (*numpy.array*) – Type of the zone ('rec' for recruitment, 'rel' for release).

Methods

<code>__init__(longitude, latitude, name, typename)</code>	Initialisation of the class.
--	------------------------------

Attributes

<code>latitude</code>	latitude getter
<code>longitude</code>	longitude getter
<code>name</code>	name getter
<code>typename</code>	typename getter

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